

Short title: Effect of LLF580, an FGF21 analog, on lipids and hepatic fat

1 **Title: Supplement to LLF580, an FGF21 Analog, Reduces Triglycerides and Hepatic Fat in obese**
2 **adults with modest hypertriglyceridemia**

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108 **Disclosure:** EMF, AN, DH, MF, YL, JK, MM, MH, DY, and ABG are employees of Novartis Institute of
109 Biomedical Research, Novartis Pharmaceuticals Corporation or Novartis Pharma AG; JD and CTB
110 completed work as an employee of Novartis Institute of Biomedical Research, JD is now employed at
111 Takeda Pharmaceuticals, Cambridge, MA and CTB is now employed at Boston Pharmaceuticals,
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117 role and is a full-time employee of Altasciences, which has received research grant/funding (institution)
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120 disclosures. Boston Pharmaceuticals, Cambridge, MA now owns the right to develop LLF580, which has
121 been renamed as BOS-580.

122 **Abstract:**

123 **Purpose:** To evaluate the safety and potential efficacy of LLF580, a genetically engineered variant of
124 human fibroblast growth factor-21, for triglyceride lowering, weight loss, and hepatic fat reduction.

125 **Methods:** A multicenter, double-blind, parallel design trial in obese, mildly hypertriglyceridemic adults
126 randomized (1:1) to LLF580 300 mg or placebo subcutaneously every four weeks for three doses.

127 **Results:** Of 64 randomized study participants, 61 (mean±SD: age 45±11 years, 49% male, 80/15/5%
128 Caucasian/African American/Other, BMI 36.1±3.8 kg/m²) received LLF580 (n=30) or placebo (n=31) at 7
129 research sites in the USA. LLF580 lowered serum triglycerides by 54% (least square mean placebo adjusted
130 change from baseline), total cholesterol 7%, LDL-cholesterol 12%, and increased HDL-cholesterol 36%
131 compared to placebo (all $P<0.001$) over 12 weeks. Substantial reduction of liver fat of 52% over placebo
132 ($P<0.001$) was also demonstrated, in the setting of improved liver function tests including alanine
133 aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, and alkaline phosphatase, the composite enhanced liver
134 fibrosis score, and N-terminal type III collagen propeptide (all $P<0.05$). Insulin and C-peptide levels and
135 insulin resistance by HOMA-IR were all lower, and adiponectin higher with LLF580 treatment compared
136 to placebo, while fasting glucose and HbA1c were unchanged. Reductions in biomarkers of bone formation
137 without differences in markers of bone resorption were observed. LLF580 was generally safe and well
138 tolerated, except for higher incidence of generally mild to moderate gastrointestinal adverse effects.

139 **Conclusions:** In obese, mildly hypertriglyceridemic adults, LLF580 was generally safe and demonstrated
140 beneficial effects on serum lipids, liver fat and biomarkers of liver injury, suggesting it may be effective
141 for treatment of select metabolic disorders including hypertriglyceridemia and non-alcoholic fatty liver
142 disease. Assessments of longer-term safety and efficacy are warranted.

143 **Supplement**

144 **Supplemental Methods**

145 **Blood pressure ascertainment:**

146 Blood pressures were obtained after the subject had been sitting for three minutes, with back supported and
147 both feet placed on the floor. Systolic and diastolic blood pressure were measured twice, with
148 approximately three minutes apart, using an automated validated device with an appropriately sized cuff.
149 In case the cuff sizes available were not large enough for the subject's arm circumference, a manual
150 sphygmomanometer with an appropriately sized cuff were permitted. If the two blood pressure
151 measurements were more off more than 5 mmHg at screening and/or baseline, an additional reading was
152 obtained, so that three consecutive assessments were made, with the subject seated quietly for
153 approximately three to five minutes preceding each repeat assessment. In case of repeated vital assessments,
154 all repeat measurements were recorded and the mean value was used.

155 **Biomarker methods:**

- 156 • Serum bone specific alkaline phosphatase(BALPI) was analyzed using Quidel BAP immunoassay
157 at Pacific Biomarkers (now Nexelis) (Washington, USA).
- 158 • Serum procollagen 1 N-terminal propeptide (P1NP) was analyzed using Roche Elecsys P1NP
159 immunoassay at Pacific Biomarkers (now Nexelis) (Washington, USA).
- 160 • Serum osteocalcin (OSTEOC) was analyzed using Roche Elecsys Osteocalcin immunoassay at
161 Pacific Biomarkers (now Nexelis) (Washington, USA).
- 162 • Serum C-terminal telopeptide (CTX-1) was analyzed using Roche Elecsys CTX-1 immunoassay at
163 Pacific Biomarkers (now Nexelis) (Washington, USA).
- 164 • Urine N-terminal telopeptide (NTX-1) was analyzed using Osteomark NTX-1 ELISA assay at
165 Pacific Biomarkers (now Nexelis) (Washington, USA).

166 Serum fibroblast growth factor 19 (FGF-19), insulin Like Growth Factor 1 (IGF-1), and total adiponectin
167 were analyzed using R&D Systems Quantikine ELISA assay at WuXi AppTec (Shanghai, China).

168 Serum N-terminal type III collagen propeptide (Pro-C3) was analyzed using Pro-C3 ELISA assay at Nordic
169 Bioscience (Denmark).

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170 Low density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol was measured directly at Clinical Reference Laboratory Inc.
171 (Lenexa, KS) due to the potential confounding of higher triglyceride levels permitted for study inclusion.

172 Enhanced Liver Fibrosis (ELF) test panel includes hyaluronic acid, amino-terminal propeptide-of-type-III-
173 collagen, tissue-inhibitor of matrix-metaloproteinase-1 (liver biomarkers).

174 **Formulas:**

175 Homeostatic model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) is calculated as: $HOMA-IR = \text{Glucose} \times$
176 $\text{Insulin} / 22.5$, where the unit of glucose is mmol/L, and the unit of insulin is mU/L.

177 NAFLD fibrosis score is calculated as $-1.675 + (0.037 \times \text{age (years)}) + (0.094 \times \text{BMI (kg/m}^2)) + (1.13 \times$
178 $(\text{IFG/diabetes})) + (0.99 \times \text{AST/ALT ratio}) - (0.013 \times \text{platelet count } (\times 10^9/\text{L})) - (0.66 \times \text{albumin (g/dl)})$,
179 where IFG is fasting glucose greater than or equal to 100.

180 Fibrosis 4 score is calculated as $(\text{Age} \times \text{AST}) / (\text{platelets} \times (\text{sqr}(\text{ALT})))$.

181 **Study Population**

182 *Inclusion criteria*

183 Study population: eligible for inclusion in this study must fulfill **all** of the following criteria:

- 184 1. Male and female subjects 18 to 65 years of age inclusive.
- 185 2. Body mass index (BMI) within the range of 30 to 45 kg/m², inclusive, with ethnic adjustment ≥ 27.5
186 kg/m² for Asian individuals (47).

187 $\text{BMI} = \text{Body weight (kg)} / [\text{Height (m)}]^2$, inclusive.

- 188 3. Fasting triglyceride 150 - 500 mg/dL (1.69 - 5.65 mmol/L), inclusive, at screening.

- 189 4. Able to communicate well with the investigator, to understand and comply with the requirements of the
190 study.

191 *Exclusion criteria*

192 Study population: fulfilling any of the following criteria are not eligible for inclusion in this study:

- 193 1. Use of other investigational drugs at the time of enrollment, or within 5 half-lives of enrollment, or
194 within 30 days, whichever is longer; or longer if required by local regulations.
- 195 2. Significant illness which has not resolved within two (2) weeks prior to initial dosing.
- 196 3. History of hypersensitivity to drugs of similar biological class, FGF21 protein analogue, or Fc fusion
197 proteins.
- 198 4. History of bone disorders including but not limited to osteoporosis, osteopenia, osteomalacia, or plasma
199 25-hydroxyvitamin D level is below the lower limit of the normal range at screening.
- 200 5. History of hepatobiliary disease, cholelithiasis, or biliary sludge by history or at screening ultrasound,
201 hepatic encephalopathy, esophageal varices, or portacaval shunt. Liver disease or liver injury as
202 indicated by abnormal liver function tests (ALT, AST, alkaline phosphatase, or serum bilirubin) above
203 upper limit of normal at screening or baseline. Patients with documented Gilbert's Syndrome or
204 cholelithiasis treated by cholecystectomy > 6 months prior to screening are not excluded, provided they
205 meet all other criteria.
- 206 6. Chronic infection with Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Hepatitis B (HBV) or Hepatitis C
207 (HCV). A positive HBV surface antigen (HBsAg) test, or if standard local practice, a positive HBV
208 core antigen test, excludes a subject. Subjects with a positive HCV antibody test should have HCV
209 RNA levels measured. Subjects with positive (detectable) HCV RNA should be excluded.
- 210 7. History of immunodeficiency diseases, or defined by a positive HIV (ELISA and Western blot) test
211 result.
- 212 8. Fasting triglycerides greater than or equal to 500 mg/dL [5.65 mmol/L], or concomitant use of drug
213 treatment for hypertriglyceridemia (fibrates, omega-3 fatty acids, nicotinic acid).
- 214 9. Active treatment with cholestyramine or colestipol resins.
- 215 10. History of pancreatic injury or pancreatitis, or other pancreatic disease. Amylase or lipase above ULN
216 at screening or baseline.
- 217 11. History of type 1 diabetes, diabetic ketoacidosis, or positive glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD)
218 antibodies.

219 12. Cushing's Disease, Cushing's Syndrome, current or recent (within 30 day) use of corticosteroids,
220 inhaled, oral, or injected.

221 13. Pharmacotherapy for osteoporosis.

222 14. Patients with contraindications to MRI.

223 *MRI contraindications include, but not limited to:*

224 • Brain aneurysm clip

225 • Implanted neural stimulator

226 • Implanted cardiac pacemaker or defibrillator, or presence of intracardiac wires

227 • Prosthetic heart valves

228 • Cochlear implant

229 • Ocular foreign bodies that might be ferromagnetic (*e.g.* metal shavings)

230 • Other implanted medical devices (*e.g.* insulin pumps)

231 • Metal shrapnel or bullets still in the body

232 • Severe claustrophobia

233 • Patients having difficulty tolerating prolonged positioning within the constraints of the MRI tube.
234 Investigators should use their best judgment to assure that patients' size will not interfere with
235 MRI imaging at any of the specified time points

236 • Tattoos (as determined by the Investigator and Imager)

237 15. Change in body weight (more than 5% self-reported OR 5 kg self-reported change during the previous
238 3 months).

239 16. Use of weight loss drugs, currently or in the past 3 months: Orlistat (Xenical, Alli), lorcaserin (Belviq),
240 phentermine-topiramate (Qsymia), naltrexone-bupropion (Contrave), or liraglutide (Victoza or

241 Saxenda) or other glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP1) receptor agonists (exenatide (Byetta/Bydureon),
242 lixisenatide (Luxumia), albiglutide (Tanzeum) or dulaglutide (Trulicity) or others), OR

243 Enrollment in a diet, weight loss or exercise program with the specific intent of losing weight, within
244 3 months prior to randomization, OR clinical diagnosis of any eating disorder is also an exclusion.

245 17. Thyroid stimulating hormone >1.5x ULN.

246 18. Poorly controlled diabetes, defined as HbA1c above 9.0%.

247 19. Poorly controlled hypertension (systolic blood pressure of 160 mmHg or more or diastolic blood
248 pressure of 100 mmHg or more) on two or more reads at screening.

249 20. Symptomatic hypotension and/or a SBP below 90 mmHg at Screening or baseline.

250 21. Renal disorder with serum creatinine of 1.5 mg/dl or more at screening.

251 22. History or current diagnosis of electrocardiogram abnormalities indicating significant risk of safety for
252 subjects participating in the study such as:

253 • Concomitant clinically significant cardiac arrhythmias, *e.g.* sustained ventricular tachycardia, and
254 clinically significant second or third degree atrial-ventricular block without a pacemaker

255 • History of familial long QT syndrome or known family history of Torsades de Pointes

256 • Symptomatic bradycardia

257 • Resting QTcF \geq 450 msec (male) or \geq 460 msec (female) at pre-treatment [baseline].

258 23. History of malignancy of any organ system (other than localized basal cell carcinoma of the skin or *in-*
259 *situ* cervical cancer), treated or untreated, within the past 5 years, regardless of whether there is evidence
260 of local recurrence or metastases.

261 24. Donation or loss of 450 mL or more of blood within eight weeks prior to initial dosing, or longer if
262 required by local regulation.

263 25. Hemoglobin levels below gender specific normal levels at screening.

264 26. Any surgical or medical condition which might jeopardize the subject in case of participation in the
265 study. The Investigator should make this determination in consideration of the subject's medical history
266 and/or clinical or laboratory evidence of any of the following:

267 • Inflammatory bowel disease, peptic ulcers, gastrointestinal including rectal bleeding;

268 • Major gastrointestinal tract surgery such as gastrectomy, gastroenterostomy, or bowel resection.

269 27. History of drug abuse or unhealthy alcohol use* within the 12 months prior to dosing, or evidence of
270 such abuse as indicated by the laboratory assays conducted during screening.*Unhealthy alcohol use is
271 defined as a history of, or current alcohol misuse/abuse, defined as "Five or more drinks on the same
272 occasion on each of 5 or more days in the past 30 days."

273 28. Heavy smoking as defined by self-report of use of 20 cigarettes or more per day.

274 29. History of recreational cannabis use within four weeks prior to dosing, or evidence of such use as
275 indicated by the laboratory assays conducted during screening. Note: This exclusion criterion applies
276 even if cannabis use is legalized where the site is located. Any prescribed, medicinal use of cannabis is
277 to be handled according to the prescription drug usage criteria defined above.

278 30. Pregnant or nursing (lactating) women.

279 31. Contraception Requirements:

280 Women of child-bearing potential, defined as all women physiologically capable of becoming pregnant,
281 unless they are using highly effective methods of contraception during dosing and for 120 days (about
282 5 to 6 times the terminal half-life) after stopping of investigational drug.

283 *Highly effective contraception methods include:*

284 • Total abstinence from heterosexual intercourse (when this is in line with the preferred and usual
285 lifestyle of the subject). Periodic abstinence (*e.g.* calendar, ovulation, symptothermal, post-
286 ovulation methods) and withdrawal are not acceptable methods of contraception.

287 • Female sterilization (have had surgical bilateral oophorectomy with or without hysterectomy),
288 total hysterectomy or tubal ligation at least six weeks before taking investigational drug. In case
289 of oophorectomy alone, only when the reproductive status of the woman has been confirmed by
290 follow up hormone level assessment.

291 • Male sterilization (at least 6 months prior to screening). For female subjects on the study the
292 vasectomized male partner should be the sole partner for that subject.

293 • Use of oral (estrogen and progesterone), injected or implanted hormonal methods of contraception
294 or placement of an intrauterine device (IUD) or intrauterine system (IUS) or other forms of
295 hormonal contraception that have comparable efficacy (failure rate <1%), for example hormone
296 vaginal ring or transdermal hormone contraception

297 In case of use of oral contraception, women should be stable on the same pill for a minimum of 3
298 months before taking investigational drug.

299 If local regulations deviate from the contraception methods listed above and require more extensive
300 measures to prevent pregnancy, local regulations apply and will be described in the informed consent
301 form (ICF).

302 Women are considered post-menopausal and not of child bearing potential if they have had 12 months
303 of natural (spontaneous) amenorrhea with an appropriate clinical profile (*e.g.* age appropriate, history
304 of vasomotor symptoms) or have had surgical bilateral oophorectomy (with or without hysterectomy),
305 total hysterectomy or tubal ligation at least six weeks ago. In the case of oophorectomy alone, only
306 when the reproductive status of the woman has been confirmed by follow up hormone level assessment
307 is she considered not of child bearing potential.

308 32. Any disorder which in the investigator's opinion might jeopardize subject's safety or compliance with
309 the protocol.

310